

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FALOLOU****FIRST NAME: Sègun Rocker****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D<****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The process of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
3. Punctuations and language variants (EUCLID 2021, 15-22; 24-32)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The subject of this course is relative of international academic writing. It is about the style rules in English to write a correct text, the choice of the words and sentence formulations. The author advises us to use Zotero for citations. In this course, the rule using of comma is explained. The module provides the basics for students on essay writing and tries to assist students in differentiating between US and UK English and being consistent in using one at a time.

In this document, I discuss about the style and how to write an academic essay writing, the different styles, and what is the best choice between UK English and US English, as far as academic research concerned in the context.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY

An academic essay is a written text that sets out certain information on a subject. The writing of an essay is governed by the necessary rules of grammar, style and spelling.

Writing an academic essay needs a lot of steps. It is important to read the text correctly and to know the subject. Understanding the meaning of the topic allows an easier redaction. It is also very important to have a plan. It is the redaction plan, the different parts of the text.

It is necessary to organize the redaction of the academic essay, which has three parts: the introduction, the body of the text, and the conclusion.

Do not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) such sweeping generalities as: "Rawls's theory of justice is the most important recent contribution to the perennial human search for the ideal society," or "Since Plato, philosophers have sought out the meaning of justice," or "For millennia, human beings have searched for truth," or "Philosophy is based on reason, not rhetoric."

Writing academic essay needs to have information on the text of the base. It is important to organize the argumentation.

For writing an academic essay, it is necessary to have an exact idea of the topic and how to organize the argumentation and others' analysis.

Do not make the writing boring and clumsy: You can introduce some stylistic variety. For example, you can inverse the sentence. Moreover, stay away from passive constructions: instead of "The wheel was invented by Joe," why not: "Joe invented the wheel." Do not have too many sentences that begin "It is..." or "There is..." Though such constructions are sometimes appropriate, overusing them slows things down. Avoid long strings of prepositional clauses. It is important to not repeat the same words.

In this publication, "The Learning Center. 2010. Essay Writing: The Basics. Sydney: University of New South", there is some rules and argues about how to write an essay.

We can talk about in academic essay, Turabian, Kate L. 1996. 'A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations.' Sixth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

A lot of publications are essays on different thematic. We can note a few authors like : Arendt, Hannah. 'The Human Condition'.1958. Reprint, Chicago : University of Chicago Press, 1998. / Hemingway, Ernest. 'The Big Two-Hearted River'. In the Nick Adams Stories, ed. Philip Young, 159-180. New York : Bantam Books, 1973.

In reading these books, we can note how the authors argue their ideas and the structuration of the document.

3) **PUNCTUATIONS**

This passage shows us the importance of punctuation in a text, the different marks, how to use it, and the difference between correct and incorrect punctuation. The general rule is to use a little time punctuation to have clear sentences. There are several punctuations mark: apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, commas, full stops, exclamation and question marks, and others... Each punctuation has a using rule and the condition of using. We can see the importance of punctuation in The Learning Center. 2010. 'Essay Writing: The Basics.' Sydney: University of New South". This reference shows the necessary elements to write an essay. In these elements, the punctuations are essential.

In the published book of Dr Scribe, it is explained how to use punctuations in sentences, especially, in Chicago style. Scribe, Abel. 2006. 'CMS Crib Sheet'. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Another book is illustrative of how to use punctuations in a text, and their important role. Cohen, Josh. 2006. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers. Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

4) **AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH**

There is a difference between American and British English. American English has influenced the language by its style because of the population size, the level of economic growth, and lifestyle. The style can be different between UK English and US English. We can have some words with different pronunciations, with the same spelling, or on the contrary.

About the periods, commas and quotation marks, it's important to note how to use the marks. By example, 'The boy kicked the ball.' (GB 'inverted commas') "The boy kicked the ball." (US "quotation marks") (cf. Neea Paatero's 'Gatsby' analysis for UK/US punctuation differences).

The "boingg" effect (cf. 'sproingg,' etc.) (N.E. Journal of Medicine 1981, then 21st

Century. In each domain, there is a difference between the UK English and the US English. In medicine, in fashionista, food terms, and others.

Then, the American English is detailed in a proper style which is celebrated as a common style language in American, explained in 'Scribe, Abel. 2006. CMS Crib Sheet. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press'. Chicago Manual Style is described as a style language which influenced the conversation, and the academic writing in USA.

A section talks about of the English style's to use in redacting an essay in Turabian, Kate L. 1996. 'A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations'. Sixth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

5) PLAGIARISM

The author does the plagiarism when he uses a source of information without giving the source of the information. Using the sentences and words of an author without mentioning it, it is plagiarism. It is necessary to put the name of the author's words and sentences or ideas we use in a document.

Plagiarism is an intellectual fault. It is a serious academic offense with big consequences. It is necessary to avoid plagiarism.

We can note the citations and the paraphrases as a method to avoid the plagiarism in a text. The name of the author can be in brackets, with the page number of the book reference.

In text citation, refers to citing the piece of work it's necessary to use within the actual text itself. For example, "Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct" (Gerson and Gerson 143). The reference (Szabist, 'A workshop on proper Academic Referencing', November 2006) is a book which explain an example of paraphrasing. Paraphrasing is different than mention a quotation with the author's name.

There are several ways of paraphrasing a text of an author. Here is the ORIGINAL text, from page 1 of Lizzie Borden: 'A Case Book of Family and Crime in the 1890s' by Joyce Williams.

About paraphrasing, it is not convenient to use the quotation marks, or to use exactly the words of the author. By example, with industry came the growth of large cities like Fall A river where the Bordens lived which turned into centers of commerce and trade as well as production (Szabist, 'A Workshop on Proper Academic Referencing', November 2006). Three large factors of nineteenth century America influenced American's life: the increase of industry, the growth of cities and the explosion of the population.

When we use a quotation, we must put the exact words in the sentences in quotation marks. The author names can be in parentheses.

At the difference in the paraphrases, we can explain only the author's ideas.

In fact, Cohen Josh, in the reference, Cohen, Josh. 2006. 'Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers'. Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Tries to explain in a few paragraphs, some rules to avoid plagiarism and to write a good essay.

Also, a lot of sentences are describing in Turabian, Kate L. 1996. 'A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations'. Sixth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. Some rules to avoid plagiarism.

Plagiarism is dangerous juridically, because it is a penal infraction and an intellectual denial.

6) STYLE GUIDE

This paragraph is about a style guide. The objective is to understand what a style guide is and what it constitutes. A writer needs a particular style guide for his text. A style guide is a way to document an approach as a writer with a lot of elements in coherence with the ideas developed. It includes technical writing and the redaction style, and it can be used in different domains. The style can have several aspects different, independently of punctuation, grammar, and others. Many different aspects can condition the style redaction as paragraph numbering and indentation, trademark or branding considerations, spelling, depth of treatment of a subject, manuscript layout, and others. For following conventions and some good references for setting style, the Strunk's 'The Elements of Style' is useful. The informations are available on website, especially the Economist style guide. By example, the Chicago manual of style which website is excellent that you can subscribe to. In order to improve your style, the BBC newstyle guide is a good reference which allows to see how one of the world's foremost news and current affairs organizations ("Organisations" in British English) handles its style.

As style guide reference, 'The University of Oxford. 2014. University of Oxford Style Guide.' Oxford: University of Oxford Press is explicated and details of rules are mentioned.

So, we can quote many references about this topic: Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. ACA-401/ACA-401D 'Coursepack: Period 1'. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University 2021.

Another reference, in Scribe, Abel. 2006. 'CMS Crib Sheet. Chicago' : The University of Chicago Press.

In Arendt, Hannah 'The Human Condition'. 1958. Reprint, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998, the style guide used is a Chicago style which is different at another style found in certain texts at England.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

This paragraph explains the Chicago style, the specifications, and how to become familiar with some examples. Chicago's manual relates the formatting of books and research papers documented. It is Turabian's manual of writers, with term papers, theses, and dissertations—1996 (Both published by the University of Chicago Press). Chicago style obeys certain rules. At the beginning of a sentence, it is not advised to use an abbreviation in lowercase, for example.

Several observations in using of Chicago style: quotations, numbers, italics and quotation marks, compound words, capitalization, and abbreviations. Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers. While sometimes

reference is made to a “Turabian style,” this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers. Revised Fall 2006.

In Chicago Manual Style, using Italics required certain rules. “Good writers use italics for emphasis only as an occasional adjunct to efficient sentence structure. Overused, italics quickly lose their force. Seldom should as much as a sentence be italicized for emphasis, and never a whole passage” (CMS 2003, 290). Add italics to a word or phrase only the first time it is used, thereafter use plain text.

About quotation’s using, “It is impossible to overemphasize the importance of meticulous accuracy in quoting from the works of others” (CMS 2003, 445). So, some changes are allowed.

In this section, we can quote like reference, Scribe, Abel. 2006. ‘CMS Crib Sheet. Chicago’: The University of Chicago Press. Which is a good reference.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS EXPRESSIONS

There are many expressions in the Latin language which is used in English. Three objectives for this chapter: to have a common understanding of Latin abbreviations used in writing, understand the meaning of Latin abbreviations, and understand the meaning of common Latin expressions.

Latin abbreviations are appropriately used in bibliographies, footnotes, and informal writing, the information in brackets, or to explain something.

It is advised to use the English equivalent of the abbreviation. It allows us to avoid misinterpretation for the reader. We have three parts: abbreviations, Latin development words, and the English equivalent.

Several Latin abbreviations are in the coursepack “Cleenewerk, Laurent and kabiru Gulma.3rd ed.2021.ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1. Bangui. Euclid University “. There are a lot of expressions and usages about it.

9) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Sample corrections to the paper concerned reading a sample response paper, the understanding of how the instructor provides a response, and learning some of the dos and don'ts of writing a response paper.

It is a template of correction that allows to the instructor to improve the document. The student can insert the corrections and the commentaries to have a best document. A lot of examples of this topic are in the publication “Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. How to write a Response Paper. Bangui. Euclid University. And another reference

is “Cleenewerk, Laurent and kabiru Gulma.3rd ed.2021.ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1. Bangui. Euclid University.

10) CONCLUSION

Writing an academic essay requires rules and a style redaction to have a structured document. The rules of grammar, spelling, and style, as well as the use of the principles of language, are essential. The student must choose between American and British English and use one at a time. The bibliography presentation should respect the disposition of information books. Plagiarism must be avoided at all costs, as it is a serious academic offense. An academic essay is a scientific document that has a lot of requirements for the student to success. Some references are recommended to approve the notions studied in this course.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerk, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University 2021
- The Learning Center. 2010. *Essay Writing: The Basics*. Sydney: University of New South Wales.
- Scribe, Abel. 2006. *CMS Crib Sheet*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- The University of Oxford. 2014. *University of Oxford Style Guide*. Oxford: University of Oxford Press
- Turabian, Kate L. 1996. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Sixth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Cohen, Josh. 2006. *Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers*. Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Purdue University, n.d. ‘Style Guide Overview’. Accessed February 09, 2022. https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/avoiding_plagiarism/guide_overview%20.html.
- The University of Sydney. n.d. ‘What are sources?’ Accessed February 08, 2022. <https://canvas.sydney.edu.au/courses/12076/pages/what-are-sources>.
- University of York, 2022. ‘Critical Reading’. Accessed February 08, 2022. <https://subjectguides.york.ac.uk/skills/critical-reading>.
- The Foundation for Critical Thinking. n.d. ‘Defining Critical Thinking’. Accessed February 08, 2022. <https://www.criticalthinking.org/pages/defining-critical-thinking/766>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.